

Management of Bowel Perforation in Typhoid Fever in A Tertiary Care Center: A Cross Sectional Study

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Abstract:

Introduction: Typhoid fever is a significant public health concern in developing countries, transmitted mainly through contaminated water or food and can lead to severe complications such as intestinal perforation. Diagnosis involves clinical symptoms, imaging tests, and serological assays. Surgical intervention is necessary in cases of perforation, with primary repair, resection anastomosis or ileostomy being common procedures depending on the severity. Challenges in managing the disease include late presentation, antibiotic resistance, and limited resources in rural areas.

Aim: To study the management of typhoid bowel perforations.

Materials and Methods: It is a cross sectional study done in the Department of General Surgery, Rohilkhand Medical College and Hospital Bareilly from 1 November 2022 to 31 October 2023. 54 patients with confirmed typhoid bowel perforations who underwent clinical evaluation, diagnostic investigations and operative intervention were in the study. Data was analyzed using descriptive statistics and appropriate tests.

Results: The study revealed that the majority of patients (81%) were males in the third decade of life, 35% presenting within 2-3 weeks of the onset of typhoid fever with symptoms of peritonitis, diagnostic tests included widal test, typhoid test and blood culture aided in the confirming the diagnosis. Surgical procedures varied based on intraoperative findings, with ileostomy being the most common. Post-operative complications such as electrolyte imbalance, weight loss, and surgical site infection were observed. Mortality rate was influenced by the pre-morbid conditions.

Conclusion: Typhoid bowel perforation remains a significant clinical challenge, particularly in resource-limited settings. The study underscores the need for comprehensive management strategies including early diagnosis, appropriate surgical intervention and adherence to evidence based guidelines. Better results were obtained with primary repair patients instead of ileostomy or resection anastomosis. Mortality of the disease does not depend on the selection of surgical procedure but can affect the morbidity.

Keywords: Typhoid fever, Bowel perforation, Resection Anastomosis, Ileostomy, Primary Repair, Complications.

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Introduction

Typhoid fever, caused by the gram-negative bacillus *Salmonella typhi*, remains a significant public health issue in many developing countries, particularly where sanitation and access to clean water are inadequate. It is commonly transmitted via the faeco-oral route and is prevalent in underdeveloped regions, causing severe complications such as intestinal perforations, which can lead to life-threatening conditions like

septicaemia and generalized peritonitis.[1] In some areas, particularly in West Africa, the incidence of typhoid-related perforation is alarmingly high, with rates ranging from 15% to 33%. In India, there are approximately 4.5 million cases annually, with a significant number of deaths.[2] Typhoid perforations typically occur in the terminal ileum due to necrosis of Peyer's patches and are more common among young adults from low

socioeconomic backgrounds.[3] Diagnosis relies on clinical symptoms, radiographic findings, and laboratory tests such as the Widal test, Typhi-dot test and blood cultures.[4] Management of typhoid perforation varies depending on the severity and includes modalities such as primary repair, resection and anastomosis or ileostomy. Surgical outcomes are often impacted by factors such as late presentation, inadequate preoperative optimization, and the presence of multidrug-resistant strains of *S. typhi*. [5] This study aims to assess whether advancements in diagnostics and medical care have improved the management of typhoid bowel perforations over time.

Materials and Method

Study Design: Cross-sectional study.

Study Setting: The present study was conducted in the Department of Surgery, Rohilkhand Medical College and Hospital, Bareilly.

Study Duration: One year, from 1 November 2022 to 31 October 2023.

Ethical Aspects: This study was conducted after taking due approval from the Institutional ethics committee.

Sample size: 54 confirmed cases of typhoid bowel perforations who underwent surgery at Rohilkhand Medical College and Hospital.

Inclusion Criteria: All patients with confirmed diagnosis of typhoid bowel perforation.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients with bowel perforations due to causes other than typhoid fever.

Pre-operative workup: Detailed clinical history and examination, with initial investigations comprising X-ray abdomen and abdominal ultrasonography. Diagnosis was confirmed using a Contrast Enhanced Computed Tomography scan in doubtful cases, supplemented by Widal, Typhi-dot test, and blood culture. Pre-operative procedural investigations included complete blood counts with hemoglobin, total leukocyte count, blood urea, serum creatinine, liver function tests, ECG, chest X-ray, and viral markers.

Data analysis: The data was entered in the SPSS (Statistical Package for social sciences) licenced version 23.0. Descriptive analysis was done by calculating proportions, means & standard deviation. Qualitative data was represented in the form of frequency and percentage. Appropriate statistical tests were applied depending on the type

and distribution of data. P-value <0.05 was considered significant.

Results

The study investigated 54 patients with typhoid bowel perforations, revealing key findings across various aspects of the disease.

The majority of patients were male (81.48%) with a median age of 32 years for males and 23 years for females. Most patients (26%) were in the 21–30 years age group.

The presenting symptoms included abdominal pain (100%), vomiting (91%), and fever (78%). Less frequently reported symptoms were constipation (15%) and loose stools (20%). On physical examination, 96% of patients exhibited abdominal distension, 94% had abdominal guarding, and 98% showed abdominal tenderness. Free fluid in the abdomen was present in 83% of patients, and 67% had absent bowel sounds (Table-1).

Diagnostic tests showed 89% positivity for the Widal test, with high positivity for Typhoid IgG (52/54) and IgM (51/54) antibodies. Blood cultures confirmed typhoid in 52% of patients, and 93% had free gas under the right dome of diaphragm on X-ray, indicating perforation (Table-2). Per-operatively all perforations were found within the ileum, with a median distance of 25cms from the ileocecal junction. Most patients (69%) had single lesions and 65% had faecal matter in the peritoneal fluid while 35% had purulent (Table-3).

Surgical interventions included ileostomy (44.4%), resection anastomosis (20.4%), and primary repair (35.2%). Complications varied by procedure: ileostomy had the highest rates of surgical site infection (42%) and weight loss (67%), while resection anastomosis was associated with higher rates of respiratory complications (64%) and septicaemia (36%). Primary repair had the lowest rates of overall complications. Mortality was 9.26%, with most deaths occurring in patients with multiple perforations. The choice of surgical procedure did not significantly affect mortality (Table-4). The average duration of hospital stay was 13.4 days. Patients who underwent primary repair were discharged the earliest (mean 11.7 days), while those who had resection anastomosis had the longest stay (mean 15.3 days) (Table-5). This comprehensive analysis provides insights into the clinical presentation, diagnostic approach, treatment, and outcomes for typhoid bowel perforations, highlighting significant variations in patient management and recovery.

Table 1: Distribution of symptoms and signs in the patients, n=54

Symptoms	Patient proportion
Pain in the abdomen	54 (100%)
Fever	42 (78%)
Vomiting	49 (91%)
Constipation	8 (15%)
Loose Stools	11 (20%)
Signs	
Distension	52 (96%)
Guarding	51 (94%)
Tenderness	53 (98%)
Free fluid	45 (83%)
Absent bowel sounds	36 (67%)

Table 2: Diagnostic tests in patients with Typhoid perforation, n = 54

Tests	n= 54
Widal test	
Positive (titre>1:160)	48 (89%)
Negative (titre<1:80)	6 (11%)
Typhoid IgG	
Positive	52 (96%)
Negative	2 (3.7%)
Typhoid IgM	
Positive	51 (94%)
Negative	3 (5.6%)
X – ray (abdomen) - free gas under the right dome of the diaphragm	
Present	50 (93%)
Absent	4 (7.4%)
Blood Culture (for Salmonella typhi and paratyphi)	
Positive	28 (52%)
Negative	26 (48%)

Table 3: Per-operative findings of patients, n = 54

Types	n = 54
Distance of perforation from ileocecal junction (cms)	
Mean ± SD	31 ± 19
Median (IQR)	25 (15, 40)
Range	5, 85
Number of perforations	
Multiple	17 (31%)
Single	37 (69%)
Peritoneal fluid	
Faecal	35 (65%)
Pus	19 (35%)

Table 4: Post-operative complication with type of surgical procedure, n = 54

Type	Ileostomy, n = 24 (44.44%)	Resection Anastomosis, n = 11 (20.37%)	Primary Repair, n = 19 (35.19%)	Total, n = 54	p-value*
Surgical site infection	10 (42%)	2 (18%)	2 (11%)	14 (26%)	0.059
Wound dehiscence	3 (12%)	1 (9.1%)	0 (0%)	4 (7.4%)	0.3
Electrolyte Imbalance	11 (46%)	4 (36%)	11 (58%)	26 (48%)	0.5
Respiratory complication	8 (33%)	7 (64%)	3 (16%)	18 (33%)	0.033
Septicaemia (blood culture positive)	6 (25%)	4 (36%)	2 (11%)	12 (22%)	0.2
Weight loss	16 (67%)	6 (55%)	4 (21%)	26 (48%)	0.011
Mortality	2 (40%)	3 (60%)	0 (0%)	5 (9.2%)	0.059

*Fisher's exact test; Pearson's Chi-squared test

Table 5: Duration of hospital stay w.r.t. procedure performed, n = 49

Procedure performed	n = 49
Ileostomy (n=22)	
Mean ± SD	14 ± 2.5
Median	13
Range	12,20
Resection Anastomosis (n=8)	
Mean ± SD	15.3 ± 1.4
Median	15
Range	14,18
Primary repair (n=19)	
Mean ± SD	11.7 ± 2.1
Median	11
Range	10, 16
Overall (n=49)	
Mean ± SD	13.4 ± 2.6
Median	12
Range	10, 20

Figure 1: Single large perforation in the ileum

Figure 2: Single perforation in ileum with faecal contamination over the bowel

Figure 3: specimen of resected segment of the ileum with typhoid perforation

Figure 4: ileo-ileal anastomosis after resection of the perforated segment

Figure 5: loop ileostomy

Discussion

Our findings provided valuable insights into the demographic, clinical, diagnostic, and management aspects of this condition, comparing them with existing literature.

The highest incidence of typhoid perforations occurred in the 21-30 year age group, followed by 11-20 years, aligning with Nilsson E. et al., who also reported a peak incidence in the 21-30 years age group.[6] The male to female ratio in our study was 4.4:1, similar to the 4:1 ratio reported by Yadav BL et al., which suggests that males are more susceptible, possibly due to higher exposure risks related to their occupational environments.[7]

All patients presented with abdominal pain, and the majority also had symptoms of vomiting and fever. These findings are consistent with Emeka CK's study, highlighting abdominal pain, fever, and vomiting as commonest symptoms. [8] Our study found that 93% of patients had free gas under the diaphragm in x-rays, slightly higher than Bansal J et al.'s report of 89.2%. [9] Blood culture positivity was 58%, aligning with the 40-60% sensitivity range described by Mather RG et al. Typhi Dot tests showed higher sensitivity compared to Widal tests.[10] For empirical antibiotic therapy we typically used Ceftriaxone and a combination therapy including Ceftriaxone and Ofloxacin with patients having higher white cell counts, later therapy was altered for individual patient based on blood culture and sensitivity results. Meropenem was initiated for patients with resistance to ceftriaxone and where first line response was seen to be inadequate.

Our study found that 59% of patients had a single perforation, with the remainder having multiple perforations. This aligns with Emeka CK, who also reported a higher incidence of single perforations. Perforations were most commonly located within 25 cm from the ileocaecal junction.[8]

Surgical procedures varied based on intraoperative findings. Ileostomy was performed in 44.4% of patients, primary repair in 35.2%, and resection with anastomosis in 20.4%. These results were in contrast with Nema AA et al.'s study, where primary repair was more prevalent. Our approach showed better outcomes in primary repair cases with minimal contamination, while late presentations required more extensive procedures.[9]

Postoperative complications included electrolyte imbalances, with hyponatremia and hypokalemia being common. The incidence of surgical site infections (26%) and wound dehiscence (7.4%) which were comparable to Mishra M et al. and Abdurrazzaq AI et al., respectively.[11],[12] Respiratory complications were significant,

especially in the resection anastomosis group, consistent with Gedik E et al.'s findings. [13] Septicaemia occurred in 22% of patients, similar to Nema AA et al.[9] The overall mortality rate in our study was 9.3%, lower than the 18% reported by Olgemoeller F et al. The mortality rate was higher in patients with multiple perforations and those undergoing resection anastomosis.[14] Average hospital stay was 13.4 days, consistent with Nilsson E et al., who reported 11 days for primary repair and longer stays for more complex procedures.[6]

Conclusion

Considering the observations of our study it can be concluded that there is still a high incidence of typhoid ileal perforation in lower socio-economic strata. Selection of surgical procedure is mostly based on the patient's condition and intraoperative findings. Mortality of the disease does not depend on the selection of surgical procedure but can affect the morbidity. After the introduction of updated WHO guidelines there are better survival chances of patients with newer antibiotic regime along with the lesser number of complications seen with lesser invasive surgery. We saw better results with patients who underwent primary repair instead of ileostomy or resection anastomosis even in the conditions where patient presented late.

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